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Photorealistic Synthetic Crowds Simulation in Indoor environments (PSCS-I): a novel synthetic dataset for realistic simulation of crowd panic and violence behaviors

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ABSTRACT Crowd analysis is a critical research field in computer vision that focuses on understanding and predicting crowd behaviors with applications extending to public safety, urban planning, and event management. However, the scarcity of large-scale, diverse, annotated datasets that can be employed for benchmarking crowd analysis-related methods has led to a stagnation in research, with many approaches already achieving near-perfect accuracy on the available datasets. In this work, we propose a novel dataset for Photorealistic Synthetic Crowds Simulation in Indoor environments (PSCS-I), generated with the state-of-the-art rendering capabilities of Unreal Engine 5, that addresses these challenges. Our dataset contains 647 photorealistic videos of long duration with high-quality annotations that support surveillance monitoring systems for crowd panic and violence behavior detection tasks. Based on this dataset, we performed a number of experiments with the current state-of-the-art crowd behavior analysis-related method, with the results demonstrating that the dataset can pose a significant challenge to multiclass behavior detection and that it outperforms the current crowd behavior analysis benchmarks on cross-dataset evaluation for abnormal crowd behavior detection. The dataset will be made publicly available upon acceptance at <https://m4d.iti.gr/results/>.

INDEX TERMS Synthetic Dataset, Crowd Analysis, Abnormal Behavior Detection, Photorealism Enhancement, Unreal Engine

I. INTRODUCTION

CROWD analysis is one of the fundamental tasks of video surveillance and has become an important technique for monitoring and analyzing large-scale public gathering events. These events (e.g., concerts, football matches, and music festivals) take place in both indoor and outdoor environments, such as theaters, stadiums, and squares, while simultaneously affecting nearby airports, malls, and transportation hubs by increasing their crowds. Particularly, the continuous increase of surveillance cameras in indoor spaces has highlighted the need for accurate indoor crowd behavior analysis systems. Unlike outdoor public spaces, indoor environments are typically characterized by tight areas, complex layouts, limited exits, and higher crowd density. These characteristics create

unique challenges such as non-linear movement patterns, bottlenecks and congestion during evacuation scenarios, and more occlusions. This necessitates that public authorities adopt innovative surveillance tools [1]–[5] that can accurately perform and ensure safety in indoor environments despite the aforementioned challenges.

Such surveillance tools are usually based on Computer Vision (CV) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms, and, together with technological breakthroughs in hardware, enable the large-scale processing and intelligence analysis of the visual content—typically captured by Closed-Circuit Televisions (CCTVs)—to detect in an effective manner potentially abnormal behaviors, such as violence and panicking [1], [4]. In particular, these tools rely on sophisticated algorithms for

various computer vision-related tasks, e.g., person detection and tracking [6], [7], crowd counting [8]–[12], and detection of abnormal behaviors [2], [13]–[15]. Most of these algorithms require a large amount of domain-specific data for their initial training in order to perform effectively in diverse settings and achieve robustness, a critical factor in surveillance systems.

Although this research field has been in continuous development, one of the main gaps is the lack of publicly available large-scale and diverse datasets for the training of crowd analysis-related algorithms. Most available datasets comprise real-world videos that are either small in scale and duration [16]–[19], captured in outdoor [17] or both indoor and outdoor [19]–[21] environments using solely a single camera type (CCTV) [17], [19], [22], or fail to capture the real-world complexities [23]–[25] and diversity [17], [22], such as variant crowd behaviors, trigger events, environments, scenes, and lighting conditions. Furthermore, capturing real-world videos and manually annotating them to generate new datasets is a resource-intensive, costly, and complex process that is not always feasible. Finally, collecting and processing real-world videos may raise ethical and privacy concerns related to the personal data belonging to individuals within the crowds.

To fill these gaps, synthetic data generation techniques [26] can be leveraged to produce large-scale datasets that can simulate multiple and diverse crowd behaviors in complex scenes and can be easily adapted to specific use cases due to the automatic creation of additional metadata. These techniques are particularly valuable for augmenting under-represented behaviors in the real world, namely, abnormal behaviors, because their existence is often scarce; however, their occurrence is essential for the effective training of AI-based algorithms. Beyond increasing the data volume, synthetic data generation also automates the annotation procedure, significantly reducing cost and eliminating any potential human error. At the same time, synthetic data vanishes any concerns about ethics and privacy protection of humans and removes human bias from the annotation process. On the other hand, these techniques require high computational resources to synthesize the data that might be sensitive to visual artifacts. Moreover, the data generated through computer graphics engines are often characterized by the simulation-to-reality (sim2real¹) gap that exists between the generated synthetic and the real-world data. This gap can be found in various aspects of a simulation, such as physics, object distribution (sim2real content gap), and the general visual realism (sim2real appearance gap), resulting in reduced performance of computer vision algorithms trained using synthetic data and applied in the real world [27]–[30].

In this work, we propose the **Photorealistic Synthetic Crowds Simulation for Indoor environments (PSCS-I)** dataset designed to address the aforementioned challenges. PSCS-I

FIGURE 1. Demonstration of four environments included in the PSCS-I dataset: (a) and (b) were captured by a CCTV, while (c) and (d) with a BWC.

is composed of large-scale and long-duration captures from both CCTV and Body-Worn Cameras (BWC), as depicted in the first and second rows of Fig. 1, respectively. In addition, PSCS-I provides a diverse range of perspectives by including a rich variety of crowd behaviors (normal, panic, and violence), trigger events, environments (Fig. 2), and extensive annotations that can support crowd behavior analysis research.

To reduce the impact of the sim2real appearance gap, we employed the Unreal Engine 5 (UE5)² in the data generation pipeline, utilizing all the latest available technologies, namely lumen³, real-time ray tracing⁴, and MetaHuman [31]. To further enhance the photorealism of the sequences and increase the scale of the dataset, we applied a State-of-the-Art (SotA) image-to-image translation method, Enhancing Photorealism Enhancement (EPE) [32], resulting in additional variations of PSCS-I. To validate the increased photorealism of the PSCS-I dataset, we quantitatively evaluated the synthetic PSCS-I compared to its photorealism-enhanced variations in terms of similarity with real-world datasets. In addition, existing synthetic datasets were also employed in the evaluation to highlight the photorealism superiority of the PSCS-I dataset.

Moreover, we employed the CrimeNet [1] architecture on the PSCS-I dataset to perform an extensive evaluation and compare it with SotA performance to illustrate the quality and significance of this dataset to the domain of crowd behavior analysis. In particular, experiments for the detection of anomalies employing within- and cross-dataset evaluations, both in a binary and in a multiclass (multi-behavior detection) manner, are reported. Comparisons with a PSCS-I subset are also included to investigate the importance and the challenges of the incorporation of the BWC captures and the multiple trigger events, along with an indoor- and outdoor-only cross-

²<https://www.unrealengine.com/en-US/unreal-engine-5>

³<https://www.unrealengine.com/en-US/tech-blog/unreal-engine-5-goes-all-in-on-dynamic-global-illumination-with-lumen>

⁴<https://developer.nvidia.com/blog/introducing-ray-tracing-in-unreal-engine-4/>

¹<https://developer.nvidia.com/blog/closing-the-sim2real-gap-with-nvidia-isaac-sim-and-nvidia-isaac-replicator/>

FIGURE 2. Illustration of 15 scenes from the PSCS-I dataset under various lighting conditions. From left to right, 1st Row: Bank, Coffee Store, Palace Hall, Prison, and Supermarket. 2nd Row: Shopping Mall, Live House, Scientific Lab, Laundromat, and Parking. 3rd Row: Factory, Bunker, Office, Storage House, and Hangar.

evaluation to examine the extensibility of the dataset to outdoor environments.

Our contributions are summarized as follows:

- 1) We propose a novel synthetic dataset for crowd panic and violence behavior detection tasks that captures multiple scenes from 26 unique indoor environments comprising more than 53.8 hours of annotated videos at a frame level, diverse lighting, various normal and abnormal behaviors, and trigger events associated with each of the abnormal behaviors.
- 2) To the best of our knowledge, PSCS-I is the first publicly available dataset that incorporates video captures using BWCs—given a growing trend in their use by law enforcement authorities—and therefore extends the available perspectives of crowd behavior analysis datasets.
- 3) PSCS-I dataset can be utilized in real-world applications by mitigating the sim2real appearance gap existing in synthetic data, through the rendering capabilities of the technologically advanced engine UE5, along with the utilization of the EPE [32] approach.
- 4) An extensive evaluation, including also cross-dataset experiments, illustrates that the proposed PSCS-I dataset can be employed to achieve SotA performance on unseen real-world data for abnormal behavior classification with potential extensibility to outdoor settings.
- 5) In addition, the dataset has demonstrated increased complexity that challenges the current SotA methods in multi-behavior crowd analysis classification, thus creating a new performance gap that enables further research in this domain.

The rest of this work is organized as follows: Section II presents an overview of the proposed crowd analysis-related real-world and synthetic datasets for crowd panic and violence detection. Section III illustrates the methodology followed for the generation of the PSCS-I dataset. Section IV describes the experimental setup, and Section V discusses

the results obtained using PSCS-I and its variations. Finally, Section VI summarizes the conclusions.

II. RELATED WORK

In this section, we present the real-world and synthetic datasets in the recent literature for crowd panic and violence detection tasks, followed by a detailed discussion of their limitations to highlight the necessity of the PSCS-I dataset.

A. REAL-WORLD DATASETS

The study of crowd analysis has led to the creation of several real-world datasets that capture scenarios such as pedestrian dynamics, group interactions, and abnormal events, supporting various crowd analysis tasks, including crowd panic and violence detection. Researchers from the University of Minnesota (UMN) proposed the UMN [19] dataset, which is one of the first crowd behavior analysis datasets. In detail, UMN primarily focuses on the detection of abnormal behaviors and contains 11 short-duration videos (4.17 minutes in total) recorded at 30 Frames Per Second (FPS), capturing normal and panic crowd behaviors. Rabiee et al. [17] proposed the Motion Emotion Dataset (MED), which focuses on crowd abnormal behaviors of panic, fight, congestion, and obstacle. MED contains 31 videos featuring one or more abnormal behaviors captured at 30 FPS with an average duration of 47.46 seconds.

To address the challenge of detecting violence in crowds, Bermejo Nievas et al. [20] proposed Movies Fights, a dataset containing 200 non-violent and 200 violent short-duration (1.74 seconds on average) captures at 30 FPS derived from various movies. Soliman et al. [33] introduced the Real Life Violence Situations (RLVS) dataset, consisting of 2,000 YouTube videos, divided between 1,000 violent and 1,000 non-violent videos depicting various human activities, such as sports, eating, and walking. The video durations range from 3 to 7 seconds and are captured at various frame rates. Perez et al. [34] created the CCTV-Fights, a violence detection

dataset containing 1,000 videos that depict violence (280) and normal (720) crowd behaviors. The captures have an average length of 45 seconds with various frame rates. Degardin et al. [35] introduced UBI Fights, a violence detection dataset incorporating 1,000 videos (80 hours) at 30 FPS; among these, 216 depict violent crowd behaviors, while the rest capture normal daily crowd activities. Aremu et al. [21] proposed the Smart-City CCTV Violence Detection Dataset (SCVD), a dataset that focuses on both violence and weapon detection by including 500 videos with a duration ranging between 5-10 seconds at 30 FPS.

B. SYNTHETIC DATASETS

The most prevalent approach when generating computer vision synthetic datasets, particularly with a focus on video surveillance applications, involves the use of the game Grand Theft Auto V (GTA-V), which provides a prebuilt environment suitable for extracting synthetic visual data [42]. Lazaridis et al. [36] introduced the Abnormal Crowd Data set (ACD), a dataset leveraging GTA-V and focusing on crowd behavior analysis. The dataset includes 14 videos at 60 FPS with an average duration of 4 minutes, depicting one of three behaviors: normal, panic, and fight. Schröder et al. [37] proposed the Crowd-Flow dataset, which was rendered (converted from the 3D world space to a 2D image) using UE4 with the ultimate goal of providing ground truth annotations for the training and evaluation of optical flow estimation methods [43]–[45]. Crowd-Flow consists of 10 videos, each ranging from 12 to 18 seconds at 25 FPS. Moreover, Crowd-Flow covers two types of crowd movements: structured crowd behavior (one or more crowds walking in different directions) and fully unstructured behavior.

Nadeem et al. [38] created the Weapon Violence Dataset (WVD) using GTA-V, containing 168 short-duration videos at 15 FPS, describing three person-to-person human behaviors: cold violence (weaponized), hot violence, and non-violence. Montulet et al. [39] proposed Grand Theft Auto 5 Event (GTA5Event), a tool that transforms GTA-V into a dataset extractor for crowd behavior analysis. Using this tool, the authors generated a multi-crowd behavior dataset that contains three unique classes: fight, flee same (e.g., crowd running towards the same direction, such as an exit), and flee random (e.g., crowd dispersing in random directions). GTA5Event comprises 54 videos captured with random frame rates in the range of 5-60 FPS.

Wei et al. [40] introduced Synthetic Abnormality DatasEt (SHADE), a synthetic dataset generated from GTA-V that simulates nine different crowd activities, including two normal (walk and social) and six abnormal (arrest, chase, fight, knockdown, run, and shoot). In detail, the dataset contains 2,149 videos with a duration of two to 34 seconds at 60 FPS. Calle et al. [41] utilized the widely adopted autonomous driving simulator CARLA [46] to generate a synthetic dataset

for panic detection. The CARLA-Panic dataset consists of 1,117 videos captured at 25 FPS, with a duration of 15 seconds for each, 10 for normal, and 5 for panic behaviors.

C. EXISTING DATASETS LIMITATIONS

To highlight the limitations of the current datasets proposed in the field of crowd behavior analysis, Table 1 lists the aforementioned datasets in chronological order for each of the two categories, real-world and synthetic, with the latter characterized by the game engine employed for their generation. It is evident that the volume of the frames for most of the real-world datasets is limited, which can pose a challenge when the goal is to achieve robust training. Additionally, the majority of the real-world datasets were collected with keywords from the web; thus, there is no control over the uniqueness and diversity of the included environments, as well as the number of individuals (characters when referring to synthetic datasets). This also limits the ability to filter the dataset for specific use cases (e.g., training only on a subset of the dataset that employs a specific camera type or environment) since they do not provide metadata. The lack of additional information related to the datasets is further reflected in the numerous unspecified numbers of environments and individuals (denoted with "-" in the table) for most of the real-world datasets. Moreover, most of the real-world datasets are explicitly focused on crowd violence detection, with the Movies Fights and RLVS datasets providing a balanced distribution between the normal and the violence classes, which can lead models to learn unrealistic scenarios where violent crowd behavior events are equally probable compared to normal behaviors.

On the other hand, the game engines and tools used for the creation of synthetic datasets are either domain-specific (e.g., CARLA for autonomous driving simulations) or are now considered outdated (GTA-V) by modern standards and are well known for exhibiting a significant sim2real appearance gap [27], [29]. Furthermore, despite the ability of synthetic data generation methods to produce large volumes of data, the available synthetic datasets have a rather limited overall scale. In addition, these synthetic datasets primarily capture a single or very few outdoor or indoor environments. Particularly, the latter stems from the fact that modeling the indoor spaces of a building's 3D model is a costly and time-consuming process. Open-world simulated environments that are typically utilized for synthetic data generation, such as the one provided in GTA-V, include a large number of buildings that are visible from the outside, but only a few (e.g., houses or banks) provide indoor spaces that are accessible and thus can be employed as scenes for simulating crowd behaviors.

Additionally, the RAGE engine employed for the development of GTA supports a maximum of 256 concurrently simulated characters [47], which can significantly impact the achievable crowd density in large-scale outdoor open-world environments such as the one included in the game. In detail, simulating a large number of characters in their highest level of quality is considered a limitation and a significant challenge for synthetic data generation. Although the CrowdFlow

⁵The number of frames in the ACD and CARLA datasets is estimated based on the average video length and frame rate.

TABLE 1. Comparison among the proposed PSCS-I and real-world and synthetic crowd behavior analysis-related datasets⁵; the "-" indicates unspecified information, and "#" denotes number.

Type	Year	Dataset Name	Camera Types	# of Frames	# of Videos	Resolution	FPS	Environment (# of)	# of Classes	# of Characters	Class Distribution	Annotation Level	Available
Real-World	2009	UMN [19]	CCTV	7, 738	11	320×240	30	Both (1)	2	-	Imbalanced	Frame	Link
Real-World	2016	MED [17]	CCTV	43, 626	31	554×235	30	Outdoor (1)	5	-	Imbalanced	Frame	Link
Real-World	2016	Movies Fights [20]	Multiple	9, 841	200	720x480 720x576	25-30	Both (-)	2	-	Balanced	Video	Link
Real-World	2019	RLVS [33]	Multiple	287, 369	2, 000	Multiple	Multiple	Both (-)	2	-	Balanced	Video	Link
Real-World	2019	CCTV-Fights [34]	Multiple	1, 798, 434	1, 000	Multiple	Multiple	Both (-)	2	-	Imbalanced	Frame	Link
Real-World	2020	UBI Fights [35]	Multiple	8, 530, 080	1, 000	640×360	30	Both (-)	2	-	Imbalanced	Frame	Link
Real-World	2024	SCVD [21]	CCTV	117, 482	500	1280x720	30	Both (-)	3	-	Imbalanced	Video	Link
RAGE	2018	ACD [36]	CCTV	201, 600	14	1920x1080	60	Outdoor (1)	3	< 256	Imbalanced	Frame	-
UE4	2018	Crowd-Flow [37]	CCTV Drone	3, 200	10	1280×720	25	Outdoor (1)	2	371 – 1, 451	-	-	Link
RAGE	2019	WVD [38]	CCTV	103, 266	168	800x500	15	Outdoor (1)	3	2	Imbalanced	Video	Link
RAGE	2021	GTA5Event [39]	CCTV	24, 000	54	2560×1440	Multiple	Both (1)	3	< 256	-	Video	Link (tool only)
RAGE	2021	SHADE [40]	CCTV	780, 000	2149	1920x1080	60	Both (1)	9	< 256	-	-	-
UE4	2023	CARLA-Panic [41]	CCTV	419, 875	1, 117	1920x1080	25	Outdoor (4)	2	25 – 150	Imbalanced	Frame	-
UE5	2025	PSCS-I (proposed)	CCTV/BWC	5, 823, 000	647	1920x1080	30	Indoor (26)	5	7 – 120	Imbalanced	Frame	Link

dataset contains a relatively large number of 1, 451 characters, the authors had to compromise in both the photorealism and the scale of the dataset, which is limited to just 3, 200 frames.

The proposed PSCS-I dataset is the first synthetic dataset that solely focuses on the unique indoor challenges by providing photorealistic visual data that has been rendered by the latest and most advanced game engine, UE5, in 26 high-quality and detailed indoor environments. Moreover, PSCS-I is the first dataset compared to both existing real-world and synthetic datasets to introduce BWC high-resolution videos, resulting in a higher number of frames compared to existing datasets, with the exception of UBI Fights. In fact, we aim to surpass UBI Fights in future work in terms of frames by extending the focus of the dataset to outdoor environments, apart from indoor ones. Considering that our goal is to preserve the same level of visual quality and scale of the dataset while increasing the number of characters to thousands, this process is expected to be significantly time-consuming with the current hardware.

III. METHODOLOGY AND DATASET GENERATION

In this section, the methodology followed to generate the PSCS-I dataset is presented, along with the dataset that was generated. In detail, the proposed methodology relies on three sequential phases: A) the generation of the initial data as exported by the selected game engine (*Synthetic Raw Data Generation*), B) the post-processing of the generated raw data into usable, high-quality annotations that can support the problem at hand, crowd behavior analysis (*Data Post Processing*), and C) the export of the processed data into the final PSCS-I dataset structure (*Modalities & Annotations*).

A. SYNTHETIC RAW DATA GENERATION

Setting up the simulation environment for the synthetic raw data generation phase (Phase A, in Fig. 3) requires the following steps: (1) the selection of the most suitable game engine for the problem at hand (Game Engine Selection); (2) the collection of related 3D assets that will be employed to visually fill the environment and execute the simulation (3D Asset Selection); (3) the definition of the logic of the simulation and the setup of the scenario (Simulation Logic &

Scenario Setup); and (4) the definition of the data extraction process that outputs the raw data outside of the simulation environment and thus the selected game engine (Raw Data).

1) Game Engine Selection

The game engine selection is a vital and critical step in the generation of a synthetic dataset, as many parameters have to be considered. For the PSCS-I dataset, UE5 was selected among the other available options (Unity Engine⁶, CRYENGINE⁷, and Godot⁸), as it is the most advanced game engine that incorporates SotA technologies such as Lumen, Nanite, MetaHuman, and MegaLights, helping to achieve renderings that faithfully approach real-world complexities (e.g., lighting rendering and its reflections). In particular, the MetaHuman technology enables the production of photorealistic characters with complex facial and body skeletal joints, resulting in highly accurate animations that are important when generating crowd simulations. Moreover, UE5 supports large-scale environments and simulations, visual programming for rapid prototyping, and multiple tools for the easy creation and customization of diverse environments.

However, the selection of UE5 necessitates addressing high computational demands and inconsistencies in the generated annotations. Regarding the computational resources, the photorealistic and large-scale simulations require large-scale processing power that is not always available and thus can significantly affect the scale of the generated datasets in terms of the number of videos, frame rate, and resolution. For the annotations, UE5 generates bounding boxes that may be inconsistent due to the camera angle, resulting in bounding boxes that might not enclose the objects [48], [49] and therefore reduce the effectiveness of the training object detection methods, e.g., YOLO, [50]. It is worth noting that this is a common issue in all the available game engines, namely, Unity, CRYENGINE, and Godot.

Overall, while UE5 requires higher computational resources, its unparalleled rendering capabilities, advanced

⁶<https://unity.com/>

⁷<https://www.cryengine.com/>

⁸<https://godotengine.org/>

FIGURE 3. Overview of the PSCS-I data generation pipeline, organized into three main phases: "Phase A" Synthetic Raw Data Generation –Step 1 Game Engine Selection: selection of the most appropriate game engine for the task; Step 2 3D Asset Selection: collection of relevant 3D assets to populate the environment; Step 3 Simulation Logic & Setup: definition of the simulation logic and scenario setup, including the character behaviors and the environmental configuration; and Step 4 Raw Data: execution of the data extraction process to generate the raw data. "Phase B" Post-Processing -Step 1 Bounding Box Generation & Filtering: the generation of the bounding boxes of visible (non-occluded) characters; Step 2 Behavior Selection: the behavior selection based on the behavior of each individual visible character; Step 3 Panoptic Segmentation: the combination of semantic and instance segmentation maps into panoptic segmentation; and Step 4 Photorealism Enhancement: the photorealism enhancement of the data based on the characteristics of two different real-world datasets. "Phase C" PSCS-I Modalities & Annotations, which include the final visual modalities and textual data of the PSCS-I dataset.

character and animation tools, and support for large-scale simulations make it the most suitable choice for generating realistic and diverse synthetic datasets. This is supported by the fact that most of the available simulators for autonomous vehicles [51] and drones [52] are built on UE4 and are planned to be upgraded to the latest version (UE5). In contrast, engines such as Unity, CRYENGINE, and Godot would require significantly more development effort and a larger team to achieve comparable levels of visual realism and simulation complexity.

2) 3D Asset Selection

After the selection of UE5 as the game engine, the next step involves the selection of all the publicly available 3D assets that are related to the problem at hand (crowd panic and violence behavior detection), including the categories

of Environments, Characters, Animations, and Visual Effects (VFX). The more assets are used, the more diverse the dataset becomes, an essential factor during Deep Neural Network (DNN) training, as it helps to prevent overfitting, improves performance, and enhances robustness.

Along those lines, a collection of 3D assets derived from FAB⁹ and the Unreal Engine Marketplace under the FAB⁹ and EPIC Content¹⁰ End-User License Agreement (EULA), respectively, is used in the PSCS-I dataset and presented below:

- **Environments:** Taking into account that the proposed dataset is focusing on crowded indoor scenes, we collected 26 unique indoor environments that represent a

⁹<https://www.fab.com/eula>

¹⁰<https://www.unrealengine.com/en-US/eula/content>

FIGURE 4. Comparison between the initial and final versions of the Storage House environment, illustrating the modifications applied for the PSCS-I dataset.

wide range of the typical characteristics of indoor architecture and can support multiple characters to simulate crowds under variable lighting conditions. These environments include: concerts (3), train/subway stations (2), museums (2), live houses (2), a bank, a coffee shop, an office, a prison, a mall, a supermarket, a hangar, a building entrance, a lab, a parking lot, a school, a stadium, a laundromat, a theme park, a police station, a factory, and a bunker. Indicative examples of some of the environments are depicted in Fig. 1, Fig. 2, and Fig. 5.

- **Characters:** Considering that crowd analysis focuses on the behavior and the dynamics of persons, the characters' features can significantly contribute to the generalization capabilities of the trained models. Thus, we collected the MetaHuman characters of the Matrix Awakens City Sample demo. These characters contain 12 heads, 10 hairstyles, six unique bodies, a wardrobe that includes tops, bottoms, and shoes in different combinations for 100 unique meshes across all the available body types, and an atlas of 60 fabric patterns.
- **Animations:** To effectively simulate crowd dynamics and therefore the dataset's behaviors, we selected various animations. Precisely, the movement of characters within a synthetic environment depends on two factors: the motion of the entire character (character controller) and the motion constrained to the 3D human shape (skeletal mesh). While the former is fully implemented by the game engine, the latter requires animation-related 3D assets. For the generation of the proposed dataset, the

following types of animations were collected, with their number indicated in parentheses: walking (7), social (39) (e.g., cheering, chatting, laughing, and waving), fighting (10) (e.g., fighting and reactions to violence), running (4), and idle (4).

- **Visual Effects:** To enhance the realism of the simulation when triggering abnormal crowd behaviors, VFX assets should be implemented. In the PSCS-I dataset, we used four VFX, two fire and two explosion; indicative examples are illustrated in Fig. 5-e in the opera house and the stadium environments.

3) Simulation Logic and Scenario Setup

Once the 3D assets are collected and selected, we need to combine and modify them in order to serve the simulation logic, initially for the characters' behavior and subsequently for the scenario setup. In particular, the simulation logic involves defining the characters' behaviors and movements, which requires significant manual effort, especially for indoor environments due to the following challenges: a) indoor environments are usually more complex due to the tight navigable space and the significantly higher amount of obstacles; hence, more sophisticated collision avoidance approaches are necessary to be applied in order to ensure seamless character movement, b) the increased number of selected animations results in a proportional increase in the number and complexity of the animation transitions; thus, it requires the careful definition and correlation of the transition combinations to ensure smooth and physically accurate movements, c) a significant portion of the selected environments does not include

FIGURE 5. Illustration of the available behaviors in the PSCS-I dataset across four different scenes: (a) and (b) showcase the two normal behaviors, while (c), (d), and (e) depict the three abnormal behaviors.

multiple rooms (i.e., for the crowd evacuation) or cannot support the defined crowd behaviors in general (i.e., some environments in their initial form lacked sufficient space to accommodate a crowd). This raised the necessity of modifying and thus building new portions of the environments to fulfill these goals. Fig. 4 illustrates the modifications that were performed on the storage house environment. As depicted, the environment initially contained a large number of fallen objects and storage racks that significantly reduced the available navigable area. Additionally, the initial connection between the rooms of the environment was not accessible due to the height and the tight navigable space.

Having implemented and addressed the simulation logic challenges, the simulation scenarios should be set up. To the best of our knowledge, the PSCS-I dataset is the first publicly available dataset that incorporates captures not only by CCTV, but also with BWCs attached to the chest of a person, similarly to how law enforcement officers typically wear BWCs in the real world. Specifically, the PSCS-I dataset includes 5-minute photorealistic videos rendered with BWCs with a 140-degree Field Of View (FOV) and CCTVs with a

110-degree FOV using a fixed resolution of 1920×1080 at 30 FPS. Additionally, in order to further enhance the diversity of the dataset, and considering that indoor spaces are not significantly affected by weather and time-of-day properties, the videos are rendered with two different light intensities: low and normal.

Furthermore, the dataset adapts a variety of normal, panic, and violence-related abnormal behaviors to accurately represent realistic dynamics in indoor spaces as depicted in Fig. 5 for four different environments. **Normal behaviors** consist of **walking** (Fig. 5-a), where characters display one of the seven walking animations, and **social** (Fig. 5-b), which features static or dynamic groups interacting at various locations utilizing a random animation from the collected 39 social animations. On the other hand, **abnormal behaviors** include **aggressive/fighting** behavior (Fig. 5-c), which occurs in crowded areas using the 10 animations related to violence and reaction to violence, **evacuation** (Fig. 5-d), where characters employ one of the four running animations to move toward exits following a trigger event; and **mixed running** (Fig. 5-e), marked by unpredictable fast-paced movements toward

nearby targets driven again by the running animations. To provide a realistic simulation of the abnormal behaviors that are crafted to mimic high-intensity scenarios, their duration is constrained to roughly 10% (i.e., 30 seconds) of the total video length of five minutes; this ensures that the occurrence of abnormal events remains low, as typically happens in the real world.

In all cases (behaviors), the four idle animations are employed when a character faces an obstacle for a short duration before rotating to another direction. In addition, the abnormal behaviors are activated by trigger events, which are designed to simulate real-world emergencies and include earthquake, fire, and explosion for **evacuation** and **mixed running** behaviors. Specifically, for the fire and explosion trigger events, the two fire and explosion VFXs are employed to visually present them in the scene during the simulation. Considering that **aggressive/fighting** behaviors can be triggered based on events that cannot be visually simulated (e.g., verbal conflicts), the subsequent competitive running action (i.e., running toward a common goal), which typically follows such triggers, is instead considered as a trigger event for such behaviors.

Additionally, the environments are classified into two categories based on their navigable surface and the total number of characters that can be smoothly navigated in the environment. Considering that PSCS-I is dedicated to indoor environments, it simulates two crowd categories, taking into account the number of characters included: small (7–50 characters) and medium (51–120 characters), with an average of 29 characters depicted per frame. In particular, the crowd count is randomized for each generated video along with the initial position, velocity, and the relative paths of the characters.

Moreover, we randomize the length of behaviors, the camera properties (i.e., location and angle for CCTV, as well as various angles and characters carrying the BWC), the time of triggering the abnormal events, the behavior sequence, and the transition delay between the behaviors during each video capture. Specifically, for the latter, a lower transition delay (5 to 10 seconds) is assigned when transitioning from a normal to an abnormal behavior compared to when transitioning from an abnormal to a normal behavior (5 to 20 seconds), since individuals typically react faster when an abnormal event occurs, e.g., fire or explosions.

Finally, taking into account that machine learning-based models are highly sensitive to imbalanced data, a balanced distribution was ensured across the camera type (CCTV, BWC), light intensity (Low, Normal), and abnormal behavior (aggressive/fighting, evacuation, mixed running), except for the trigger events, which were equally distributed among the behaviors to maintain representational fairness. This approach resulted in a set of 12 unique scenarios, obtained by combining all possible configurations among 2 camera types, 2 lighting intensities, and 3 abnormal behaviors, leading to an equal number of videos per environment, as presented in Table 2. Noteworthy, the percentage of frames that depict abnormal related classes (positive rate), namely the evacuation, mixed running, and aggressive/fighting behaviors, is

imbalanced with a ratio of 5.93%.

TABLE 2. Scenario setup after balancing the camera type, light intensity, behavior, and trigger event properties, resulting in 12 videos for each selected environment of the PSCS-I dataset.

Camera Type	Light Intensity	Abnormal Behavior	Trigger Event
CCTV	Normal	Mixed running	Earthquake
CCTV	Normal	Aggressive/Fighting	Competitive Running
CCTV	Normal	Evacuation	Explosion/Fire
CCTV	Low	Mixed running	Explosion/Fire
CCTV	Low	Aggressive/Fighting	Competitive Running
CCTV	Low	Evacuation	Earthquake
BWC	Normal	Mixed running	Earthquake
BWC	Normal	Aggressive/Fighting	Competitive Running
BWC	Normal	Evacuation	Explosion/Fire
BWC	Low	Mixed running	Explosion/Fire
BWC	Low	Aggressive/Fighting	Competitive Running
BWC	Low	Evacuation	Earthquake

4) Data Extraction & Raw Data

To derive the required raw data for composing the PSCS-I dataset, the data extraction process is also a crucial component of the simulation in order to achieve (a) optimized and reduced raw data generation time and (b) the ability to expose information that is required for the photorealism enhancement process and is integrated deep into the engine, namely G-Buffers and image segmentation. As illustrated in step 4 (Raw Data) of the synthetic raw data generation phase (Phase A) in Fig. 3, each rendered simulation frame is accompanied by corresponding visual and textual annotations. In detail, in the PSCS-I dataset 12 unique semantic classes (unlabeled, ground, vehicle, terrain, vegetation, infrastructure, lights, signs, props, building, sky, and character) were selected in the form of semantic segmentation masks (label maps) in order to follow the same annotation scheme used for the photorealism enhancement model [27], [32]. Specifically, all the aforementioned semantic classes are present in the dataset, including the terrain and sky classes, since some of the selected environments have visibility to the outdoor portions of the virtual world through transparent windows or open doors. However, the frequency of pixels that correspond to these classes is significantly lower compared to other classes, namely person, ground, and building, which are present in every frame of the PSCS-I dataset. The annotation process of the semantic classes in a synthetic environment can be a significantly time-consuming procedure, especially for larger and more complex environments that can contain thousands of (non-grouped) 3D assets. On the other hand, for the rest of the image segmentation annotations that contain the character instances and the head instances, this process is straightforward since the instance identifiers (IDs) for each of the characters can be defined and updated dynamically.

The G-Buffers, which are additional information derived from the engine for the purpose of enhancing the photorealism of the synthetic data, include six buffers (depth, metallic, specular, roughness, world normals, and base color). Similarly to the selection of the semantic classes, these specific G-Buffers were exported since they are required as input in the pretrained photorealism enhancement models [27].

Particularly, these G-Buffers provide additional information about the geometry, lighting, and materials of the virtual environment. To optimize the data extraction process and reduce the raw data extraction time, the grayscale buffers, namely metallic, specular, and roughness, were encoded into a single RGB image, resulting in four frames. Additionally, 16 skeletal joints of the entire character skeleton (spines (3), head (1), thighs (2), arms (4), hands (2), feet (2), and calf (2)) were projected in the screen space (2D coordinates) and extracted for each of the characters in the environments despite their occlusion state (if the character is visible in the frame). These skeletal joints were selected as they are widely used in pose estimation datasets [53]. While the MetaHumans are structured by hundreds of skeletal joints, exporting all of them would result in a substantial increase in computational time during the generation of the raw data (phase A). Finally, the data extraction process exports textual annotations related to the simulation setup and the properties of the camera and the environment, such as the environment name, the light intensity, the trigger event name, and the camera type and FOV.

B. DATA POST-PROCESSING

To deal with the limitations of UE5 and provide highly accurate crowd behavior annotations accompanied by photorealistic visual data, our methodology relies on three post-processing steps applied to the generated raw data (Phase B, in Fig. 3). Initially, the bounding box extraction and filtering step is employed to identify non-occluded characters, followed by the calculation and selection of their behavior, and finally, by the photorealism enhancement of the captured scene to reduce the impact of the sim2real appearance gap.

1) Bounding Box Generation & Filtering

The game engine provides pixel-level annotations at the instance level of the 3D assets that are depicted in the final rendered image. Specifically, the characters used in the PSCS-I dataset are split into two parts: head and body. This enables the generation of instance masks for each character (union of head and body) and for each character's head, and thus the extraction of bounding boxes from the binary masks. However, this approach is subject to several challenges, including the significant occlusion of the head or the entire character, as well as the head and character bounding box overlapping as a result of the occlusion of the rest of the body part (excluding the head).

Relying on a white pixel threshold in the binary mask of each of the character or head instances is not sufficient to filter significantly occluded bounding boxes, since it is dependent on distance. To illustrate, a partially occluded character near the camera will occupy a larger portion of the pixels of the image compared to a distant non-occluded one due to its larger size. To overcome this challenge, we adopted an approach for bounding box filtering that employs the extracted skeletal joint annotations of the characters and compares them with the values (on the same location) on the

instance segmentation mask derived from the engine for each character, as depicted in step 1 of phase B in Fig. 3. In detail, for each character, skeletal joints are represented as 2D pixel coordinates within the frame. The visibility of each joint is determined by evaluating the corresponding pixel value in the character's binary instance mask. Specifically, a joint is classified as visible if the mask value at its location is one (white) and occluded otherwise (mask value of zero, black). To be aligned with COCO [54] annotation standards, at least one joint is required to be visible in the frame in order to generate the bounding box.

On the other hand, head bounding boxes require a slightly different strategy due to their smaller 3D geometry and the availability of only a single skeletal joint (head). Instead of relying solely on joint visibility, we filter the bounding boxes based on a small pixel threshold (at least 2 pixels in width and height, similar to [50]), while maintaining bounding boxes smaller than the threshold only in the case where the head skeletal joint is visible. This approach ensures that bounding boxes for distant character heads are preserved only when they are significantly visible. Finally, since bounding boxes are generated for both the entire character (i.e., the union of head and body) and the head-only region, an additional mechanism is introduced to prevent duplicate bounding boxes in cases where only the head is visible. To achieve this, the head pixels within the character's binary mask are suppressed by subtracting one from the head binary mask and multiplying the result by the entire character instance binary mask, therefore producing a body-only binary mask (see eq. 1). This mask is subsequently used to determine whether any white pixels remain in the body region. If white pixels are present, a bounding box is generated for the entire character; otherwise, no additional bounding box is created, as it would be identical to the one derived for the head.

$$\text{Mask}_{\text{body}} = \text{Mask}_{\text{character}} \cdot (1 - \text{Mask}_{\text{head}}) \quad (1)$$

2) Behavior Selection

In the real world, people reacting to events (e.g., explosions, gunshots, visible fires or smoke, and aggressive fights) have a unique response time that may vary. Similarly, in the simulations of the PSCS-I dataset, instead of directly defining the behavior class of each frame by simultaneously updating all the characters to instantly perform one of the implemented behaviors, we adopted a dynamic transition approach where the behaviors are defined at the character level.

In order to define the behavior for each frame, we consider the characters whose bounding boxes result from the bounding box generation and filtering (see Section III-B1). In detail, the bounding boxes define the visible (non-occluded) characters of the frame, and since the supported behaviors are annotated at the character level, each bounding box is annotated with one of the five behavior classes (walking, social, aggressive/fighting, evacuation, and mixed running) included in the PSCS-I dataset. Thus, the distribution of behaviors per frame is then obtained by calculating the proportion of

bounding boxes assigned to each of the five classes. The final behavior annotation of the frame is the one that reaches a threshold that is experimentally set to 60% of the bounding boxes. Considering that occlusions may cause multiple short-duration behavior classes to appear during the transition period when the threshold is reached, we require each behavior's duration to last for a specific number of consecutive frames, experimentally set to 100. In this case, the frame is annotated with the same behavior that was selected in the previous frame of the video sequence.

Moreover, when there are no visible characters, which is likely for BWC perspectives, the behavior is determined based on the speed of the character to which the BWC is attached. If the speed falls within the walking range (0–140 unreal units¹¹), the frame is annotated as walking. Otherwise, the ground-truth behavior of the character to whose chest the BWC is attached is assigned to the frame. Since the selection process for generating the behaviors described in this section is generated by an algorithm, it ensures consistent and unbiased behavior annotations across the entire PSCS-I dataset by using a specific threshold for determining whether a frame is characterized as abnormal or normal; hence, minimizing the annotation bias, a common issue in real-world data annotation processes.

Finally, the dynamic aspect of the behavior transition and selection described in this subsection also distinguishes the characteristics of the trigger events that accompany the abnormal crowd behaviors from the characteristics of the crowd behaviors themselves. The trigger events, namely explosion/fire and earthquake, are initially triggered at the start of the transition process. Along those lines, frames that depict a fire/explosion trigger event or are affected by the shake of the camera can still be annotated as normal (i.e., walking or social) until the characters start reacting and reach the threshold of 60%. With this approach, deep-learning models will not be able to achieve perfect accuracy just by relying on the explosion/fire visual features or the camera movement of the earthquake event to classify if a frame is normal or abnormal, but have to be able to focus and analyze the dynamics of the crowd despite the challenging conditions introduced by the events (e.g., camera shake).

3) Panoptic Segmentation

Panoptic segmentation is a type of image segmentation that combines *semantic segmentation*—which assigns a class label to each pixel—with *instance segmentation*—which distinguishes between individual object instances—into a unified representation as depicted in Fig. 6-b. In the PSCS-I dataset, both semantic segmentation maps and instance masks for characters and heads were generated during the raw data generation phase (Phase A). To create the final panoptic segmentation maps, we merged the semantic segmentation with both character and head instances.

¹¹In Unreal Engine, by default, one unreal unit (uu) is equivalent to one centimeter (cm).

FIGURE 6. Visual demonstration of the available annotations and modalities in the PSCS-I dataset. (a) Enhanced RGB imagery with improved photorealism, tailored to resemble the visual characteristics of the real-world datasets KITTI and Cityscapes. (b) Panoptic segmentation combining semantic labels for the environment and instance-level labels for each character body and head. (c) Depth maps providing per-pixel distance information between the camera and the environment. (d) Bounding boxes for detecting both the characters and their heads.

To achieve this, the semantic segmentation labels were first included after removing the character class, resulting in 11 semantic categories labeled with IDs from 0 to 10. Then, character instance IDs were added by offsetting their original IDs by 11 to avoid overlap with semantic class IDs. Finally, the head instance IDs were added by applying an additional offset equal to the maximum number of active characters of the video that the panoptic segmentation corresponds to, denoted as MaxCount. Since the character and head instances are merged, the final panoptic segmentation mask contains the body-only and head instance IDs that are defined within the following ranges:

The body instance IDs are defined within the range:

$$10 < ID \leq 10 + \text{MaxCount} \quad (2)$$

and the corresponding head instance IDs fall in the range:

$$10 + \text{MaxCount} < ID \quad (3)$$

This ID assignment enables the retrieval of a head instance ID corresponding to a given body ID by applying the offset $ID_{\text{head}} = ID_{\text{body}} + \text{MaxCount}$, given that each character has a one-to-one mapping between body and head.

4) Photorealism Enhancement

To enhance the photorealism of the proposed dataset by reducing the visual artifacts, which is important when the goal is to deploy the trained models in the real world, we employed two Generative Adversarial Network (GAN)-based EPE [27] models. These models rely on additional information generated by the game engine, namely the G-Buffers, and aim to translate the synthetic frames rendered by UE5 towards the visual characteristics of the real-world datasets, Cityscapes [55] and KITTI [56]. In particular, these models were trained on a synthetic dataset generated through the

CARLA simulator [57], which is based on UE4, utilizing 10 G-Buffers (scene color, albedo, subsurface color, screen space ambient occlusion, normals, depth, metallic, specular, roughness, stencil). As described during the raw data generation phase (Phase A), all the required G-Buffers, along with the semantic segmentation maps (stencil) for each rendered frame, were extracted from the game engine. However, since Screen Space Ambient Occlusion (SSAO) is disabled when Lumen is enabled in UE5, we randomly generated the ambient occlusion. In fact, we visually observed that this approach didn't result in any visual artifact. This indicates that the photorealism enhancement models do not heavily rely on that particular G-Buffer during the translation process.

Specifically, the EPE architecture processes these G-Buffers by a G-Buffer encoder, which consists of multiple Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) streams for each defined semantic class. Thus, EPE learns to enhance the photorealism individually for an object or group of objects based also on their material and geometry properties as defined by the G-Buffers, rather than the entire scene, and enables its ability to ignore semantic classes from the translation process. This makes EPE a robust method that can generalize even on synthetic indoor scenes despite being trained on synthetic images of the CARLA simulator towards the characteristics of the Cityscapes and KITTI datasets, which are all based in outdoor urban settings.

For the usage of generative AI techniques, such as EPE, on the generated data, we had to take into account the number of 3D assets whose usage is not permitted and filter them out. Hence, from the 312 generated videos resulting from the execution of the aforementioned 12 scenarios in 26 environments in step 2 of phase A, 216 were selected for the application of the EPE models trained to target the visual characteristics of the two datasets, Cityscapes and KITTI. Additionally, due to the significant storage requirements and the scale of the proposed dataset, the G-Buffers were generated in lower quality. This approach led to some corrupted frames in the case of the enhanced KITTI videos. As a result, only a subset of 119 videos from 216 that were enhanced with the KITTI characteristics could be utilized by tasks that require sequential data, such as crowd behavior analysis, resulting in a final set of 335 photorealism-enhanced videos.

C. PSCS-I MODALITIES & ANNOTATIONS

This section describes first the modalities that comprise the PSCS-I dataset and subsequently the corresponding annotations.

1) Modalities

The PSCS-I dataset consists of 312 **rendered videos** that are generated from the frames that were rendered through the UE5 rendering pipeline (denoted as PSCS-I Synthetic). Moreover, the application of step 4 in the post-processing phase of the photorealism enhancement (see Section III-B4) enriches the dataset with an additional 335 **enhanced videos** (denoted as PSCS-I Enhanced), resulting in a union of 647

videos (denoted as PSCS-I Union) stored in Audio Video Interleave (AVI) format. Indicative examples are depicted in Fig. 6-a.

Panoptic segmentation, as illustrated in Fig. 6-b, corresponds to the result of the third post-processing step by combining semantic and instance segmentation maps. Particularly, panoptic segmentation can be valuable for extending the PSCS-I dataset for additional tasks related to crowd analysis. To illustrate, dot annotations can be extracted for crowd counting by calculating the centroid of the white pixels in each character's head instance binary mask.

Moreover, the **depth** information of the scene describes the distance from the camera to the world location projected for each pixel in the screen space. This information is automatically generated by UE5, and it is derived from the Z-Buffer of the deferred rendering pipeline. Due to the high storage space requirements for the depth information, we limited the support of depth to 100 meters, which is suitable for indoor environments, and we provide it in a compressed 2D array format. Indicative examples are depicted in Fig. 6-c.

2) Annotations

The **bounding boxes** were generated and filtered in order to extract the behavior of the visible characters and select the final behavior annotation of each frame in the postprocessing step (see Section III-B1). Since the bounding boxes can be employed in crowd analysis also for tasks related to person detection and crowd counting, we provide the 2D bounding boxes for both the characters and the characters' head classes (Fig. 6-d) defined in a standard coordinate-based format, along with the widely adopted COCO and YOLO formats.

Finally, the **textual** annotations are provided through two JSON-structured files. The first file contains five fields for each video of the PSCS-I dataset, namely the per-frame behavior classes in both a binary and multiclass classification manner (see Section III-A3), the proposed split (train, validation, or test), the name of the abnormal class, and the availability of an enhanced version. The second file provides the details of the selected environment and the setup specifications of the simulated scenarios (i.e., environment name, camera properties, light intensity, data split, trigger event name, and the maximum number of characters), which can be utilized for filtering the dataset to each researcher's needs.

D. HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

For each phase in the dataset generation pipeline, the hardware requirements and the time needed are illustrated. In phase A: a system equipped with an Intel CPU (i7-14700F), an NVIDIA GPU (RTX 4090 with 24GB VRAM), and 64GB of system RAM, running Windows 11 as an Operating System (OS), requires approximately 30 minutes to render each video (6.5 days in total). In phase B: a server equipped with an Intel Xeon CPU (W-3375), an NVIDIA GPU (RTX A6000 with 48GB VRAM), and 256GB of system RAM, running Ubuntu 22.04, averages 1.5 hours per video for the first three steps

and requires roughly 1.5 days to enhance the photorealism of a batch of 12 videos during the fourth step (42.6 days in total).

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this section, the experimental setup for the performance evaluation of the PSCS-I dataset and its variations is described. First, the selected method and benchmark datasets are presented. Then, the experimental categories, which include both within-dataset and cross-dataset evaluations, are provided. Finally, the evaluation metrics used for the quantitative comparison are outlined.

A. BENCHMARK MODEL

To illustrate the performance of the PSCS-I dataset and its effectiveness in crowd panic and violence detection tasks, instead of reporting the performance of multiple benchmark models on the proposed PSCS-I dataset, an approach typically followed by other works [36], [38], we opted for a single method. This approach enables the direct comparison with multiple panic- and violence-related datasets and better highlights the contributions of the dataset, including the photorealism enhancement, the BWC, and trigger events, which are both first introduced in PSCS-I. Moreover, finding a crowd behavior analysis method that performs classification at the frame level (similarly to the annotations of PSCS-I, which are frame level) is also challenging, considering that most of the approaches are not publicly available or focus on video classification of violence behaviors, such as Video Vision Transformers (ViViT) [58], 3D ResNet [2], [59], Convolutional LSTM [5], and ViolenceNet [3] (additional comparisons for violence detection are provided in Appendix B). Along those lines, we selected the architecture of CrimeNet [1] since it is the only architecture that reports SoTA performance on the most challenging crowd behavior datasets and offers a simple, publicly available implementation. Specifically, CrimeNet has achieved near-perfect accuracy on a variety of violence and crime detection benchmarks [34], [35], [60], [61], mitigating the false positives that can pose a limiting factor in security monitoring systems. Therefore, CrimeNet is an ideal method to showcase that the PSCS-I can challenge even the most robust approaches for crowd behavior analysis.

In our experiments, we employed the CrimeNet architecture as defined in its official repository¹² with the default parameter and data loading configuration. In detail, the CrimeNet architecture is based on a Vision-Transformer (ViT) and utilizes both the video RGB frames and the optical flow between two consecutive frames transformed by the Gunnar-Farneback algorithm [62]. To deal with large-scale datasets and the intensive computational requirements of calculating and storing optical flow, CrimeNet resizes the video frames at a small resolution of 20×20 . During batch loading, these are rescaled to 224×224 (the typical input resolution of ViT) and are normalized by subtracting and then dividing by 127.5 (tanh normalization). Considering that the method

relies on adversarial learning, no further augmentation is applied to the video frames (e.g., random cropping or flipping).

B. BENCHMARK DATASETS

For the PSCS-I dataset, the available variations were utilized, namely the PSCS-I Synthetic, PSCS-I Enhanced, and PSCS-I Union. Regarding the PSCS-I Union variation, we ensured that there is no overlap between sets in the PSCS-I Synthetic and the corresponding PSCS-I Enhanced videos. In particular, a rendered video used in the training set and its corresponding photorealism-enhanced variation cannot appear in different sets (i.e., the enhanced variation will also be employed as a training sample). Along those lines, both training and evaluation were performed using a split of 70% for training, 20% for validation, and 10% for testing, which is a standard setup for crowd behavior analysis tasks.

To facilitate a comprehensive evaluation using the PSCS-I dataset, additional benchmark datasets were employed for training CrimeNet, extending beyond the crowd violence datasets used in its original paper [1], namely UBI Fights, CCTV Fights, XD-Violence [60], and UCF-Crime [61]. Notably, UMN, MED, Movies Fights, SCVD, and synthetic WVD were selected for their diversity in scale and their inclusion of a wide range of behavior classes, such as violence, panic, and other abnormal scenarios (e.g., weaponized and abnormal objects), with some of these behaviors not being present in the PSCS-I dataset. This allows for evaluating the generalization capabilities of the model (trained on the proposed dataset) and particularly its ability to detect behaviors that were not included in the PSCS-I dataset and thus not seen during training.

In detail, the UMN and MED datasets were selected as they are the standard benchmarks employed for evaluating both panic [63], [64] and abnormal behavior [13], [15] detection methods. Concentrating on the larger number of publicly available violence detection datasets, UBI-Fights and CCTV-Fights, which are both imbalanced datasets and annotated at the frame level, UBI-Fights was selected since it provides 6,731,646 additional annotated frames (see Table 1) compared to CCTV-Fights. XD-Violence and UCF-Crime, which were also employed to benchmark CrimeNet, were not employed in the experiments since they are crime-related datasets designed for weakly supervised learning (videos annotated as abnormal also contain segments of normal crowd behaviors without frame level annotations). Specifically, both include classes, such as car crashes and explosions, that are not relevant to analyzing crowd dynamics. The explosion class also contradicts the goal of the PSCS-I to use the explosion/trigger to challenge the classification of the behaviors without solely relying on the visual features or motion introduced in the optical flow by the explosion itself.

Furthermore, between the Movies Fights and RLVS datasets, which are both balanced datasets annotated at the video level, Movies Fights was selected since it contains social-like normal behaviors (e.g., walking and waving) of individual persons. While RLVS contains a larger volume

¹²<https://github.com/FernandoJRS/CrimeNet-ViT-NSL>

of frames, most of them are from a similar domain and specifically from sports games (e.g., football and Olympic games). SCVD was also selected, as it is the only real-world violence-related dataset for multiclass classification. On the other hand, synthetic WVD was the only publicly available synthetic dataset suitable for our experimental setup. CrowdFlow is also available and contains various crowd behavior patterns. However, it is currently annotated only with optical flow fields, person trajectories, and dense pixel trajectories, and thus requires additional manual annotation to be utilized for crowd behavior classification. To this end, we employed CrowdFlow only for the quantitative evaluation of the effectiveness of the photorealism enhancement.

Overall, we employed the datasets listed below, along with their characteristics:

- **UMN** [19], proposed for binary classification, provides a single video without any predefined split. It includes frame level annotations with an imbalance towards the panic class, which has a positive ratio of 18.61%.
- **MED** [17], proposed for multiclass classification of abnormal behaviors, includes 32 videos without any predefined split. It is annotated at the frame level with an imbalance towards the abnormal classes, which have a positive ratio of 31.76%.
- **Movies Fights** [20], proposed for binary classification, contains 100 videos for each class without a predefined split. It is annotated at the video level, with a positive ratio of 50% for the violence class.
- **UBI Fights** [35], proposed for binary classification, consists of 1,000 videos separated in predefined splits. It is annotated at the frame level with an imbalance towards the violence class, which has a positive ratio of 2.84%.
- **SCVD** [21], proposed for multiclass classification of abnormal behaviors, contains 500 videos separated in predefined splits. It is annotated at the video level with an imbalance towards the abnormal-related classes, which have a positive ratio of 64.60%.
- **WVD** [38], a synthetic dataset for multiclass classification, includes 168 videos without any predefined split. The dataset is imbalanced towards the abnormal classes with a positive ratio of 33.51%.

For the benchmark datasets, the predefined splits were used when available, except for MED, MoviesFights, and synthetic WVD, which were unavailable and were thus split into 80% for training, 10% for validation, and 10% for testing to be aligned with the default configuration in the CrimeNet implementation and ensure a slightly larger training set, which is particularly beneficial given the limited scale of the aforementioned datasets. In detail, CrimeNet employs a stratified shuffle split to generate training, validation, and testing subsets that contain approximately the same class distribution as the whole dataset. For datasets with already predefined splits, only random shuffling is applied before training.

C. EXPERIMENTAL CATEGORIES

To illustrate the advantages of the PSCS-I dataset in the domain of crowd analysis, three categories of experiments were conducted. The first category focuses on the performance evaluation of the abnormal behavior detection formulated as a **binary classification** problem for using both balanced and imbalanced datasets. The second category of experiments includes a **cross-dataset binary classification** evaluation to illustrate the generalization capabilities of models trained using the PSCS-I dataset and the contribution of the photorealism enhancement in the reduction of the sim2real appearance gap, as robustness is more than critical in crowd analysis tasks. The third category of experiments is particularly focused on the crowd behavior classification, which is formulated as a **multiclass classification** problem to illustrate the effectiveness of the models trained using the PSCS-I dataset in the detection of multiple crowd behaviors.

For binary classification experiments, the normal and abnormal-related classes of the multiclass behavior datasets were merged into two distinct categories: normal and abnormal. For the PSCS-I dataset, the classes are already provided in both multiclass and binary formats, as illustrated in phase C of the PSCS-I dataset generation (Fig. 3). For the benchmark datasets: in MED, panic, fight, and congestion; in SCVD, violence and weaponized; and in WVD, hot and cold violence were considered as the abnormal class. Since most of these datasets contain only a single normal class, it remained unchanged except for MED, where neutral was merged with the nothing class. The class ratio for the datasets that were initially imbalanced (MED, SCVD, and WVD), containing multiple abnormal-related classes, and therefore merged, remains imbalanced after the merging assumption. For the UMN and UBI Fights that already provided for binary classification, are imbalanced, except for the Movies Fights, which is balanced.

Regarding the cross-dataset evaluation, we first performed a quantitative evaluation (for qualitative evaluation, see Appendix A) to quantify the effectiveness of the photorealism enhancement method and investigate the photorealism superiority of the PSCS-I dataset compared to existing synthetic datasets. Particularly, we employed the synthetic PSCS-I frames (PSCS-I Synthetic), the same frames after applying the photorealism enhancement method towards the characteristics of Cityscapes (PSCS-I Enhanced-Cityscapes) and KITTI (PSCS-I Enhanced-KITTI), and the frames of the synthetic WVD and CrowdFlow datasets. To this end, each set of frames was evaluated in terms of similarity with Cityscapes and KITTI (the datasets that the photorealism enhancement method was trained on), and the real-world crowd behavior analysis related datasets, UMN, MED, Movies Fights, UBI Fights, and SCVD. After evaluating the photorealism of the PSCS-I dataset to illustrate the generalization capabilities on the task at hand (crowd behavior classification), we compared the performance of the respective models against the test sets of the real-world datasets (UMN, MED, Movies Fights, and UBI Fights) as the main objective of synthetic data is to be uti-

lized for training models that are to be employed in real-world applications. Along those lines, the PSCS-I variations that include the enhanced videos, namely, PSCS-I Enhanced and PSCS-I Union, were also employed since their contribution has been proven significant only when cross-evaluating on real-world data [27]. In fact, conducting cross-domain evaluation exclusively on real-world data is the common approach when performing domain adaptation through image-to-image translation in both crowd analysis [65] and other scientific domains such as autonomous driving [28]. To preserve fairness in the experimental comparisons for datasets that are not provided with predefined splits by the authors, namely, UMN, MED, and Movies Fights, the entire dataset is employed as a test set for cross-evaluation. In addition, to investigate the contribution of the introduced trigger events and the BWC perspective in terms of generalization, the aforementioned classification experiment was also conducted on a filtered subset of the PSCS-I Synthetic variation, referred to as PSCS-I Synthetic Static. In the PSCS-I Synthetic Static subset, all videos containing earthquake events or those captured from a BWC were removed. This ensured that all remaining videos featured static scenes, without any camera motion caused either by the earthquake trigger event or character movement captured through BWC.

Finally, we utilized the single dataset that provides meta-data related to the environment type (indoor or outdoor), UBI Fights. This resulted in two subsets of the dataset, namely UBI Fights-Indoor and UBI Fights-Outdoor, that were utilized to cross-evaluate the models trained on the PSCS-I Synthetic, PSCS-I Enhanced, and PSCS-I Union variations to investigate the extensibility of the proposed dataset to outdoor environments and the impact on the accuracy.

For multiclass classification, no cross-dataset evaluation was performed since there is no available benchmark that matches the classes of the proposed dataset; hence, the experiments are limited to a within-dataset evaluation setup performed by training the CrimeNet architecture on the available multiclass classification datasets (MED, SCVD, WVD, and PSCS-I Synthetic) and testing on the respective test set of each of the datasets. Moreover, to illustrate the influence of the introduced trigger events and the BWC perspective in the multi-class classification performance, the PSCS-I Synthetic Static subset was also employed.

D. EVALUATION METRICS

In this subsection, we describe and define the metrics that were employed in the experiments for both evaluating the effectiveness of the photorealism enhancement method applied on the PSCS-I dataset and the classification accuracy of the trained CrimeNet models.

1) Similarity Metrics

To evaluate the similarity between generated and real images, FID (Fréchet Inception Distance) [66] and KID (Kernel Inception Distance) [67] are two of the most commonly employed metrics. In particular, KID has been proven to be su-

perior compared to FID [67], while it provides more reliable results, especially with smaller sample sizes. In detail, KID is calculated on features extracted from both the generated and the real images using an InceptionV3 [68] architecture. Then, KID is calculated using the Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) with a polynomial kernel between real and generated feature sets.

While KID provides more reliable results compared to FID, there are still several limitations, including dependence on inception embeddings, limited semantic coverage (inception was trained on a fixed set of 1,000 classes), assumption of distribution similarity, and sample size sensitivity. Additionally, KID does not always align with human perception of image quality or diversity. To solve these issues, in [69], the CLIP Maximum Mean Discrepancy (CMMD) metric was proposed, which utilizes richer CLIP embeddings and MMD with the Gaussian Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel. In detail, CMMD is an unbiased estimator and, compared with the previous metrics, namely FID and KID, does not make any additional assumptions related to the probability distribution of the embeddings. Moreover, through experimentation, CMMD was proven to better align with human perception and judgment related to the most visually appealing generated result among different models.

2) Classification Metrics

The classification evaluation was carried out using the Receiver Operating Characteristic Area Under the Curve (ROC AUC) [70] and the Receiver Operating Characteristic Precision-Recall (PR AUC) metrics [71]. Both metrics aim to evaluate the performance of binary classification models.

In particular, ROC AUC measures the model's ability to distinguish between positive (abnormal behavior) and negative (normal behavior) cases as depicted in Eq. (9). In detail, ROC AUC is calculated based on the True Positive Rate (TPR) (Eq. (6)) and False Positive Rate (FPR) (Eq. (7)), which measure the proportion of the actual positives that were correctly identified and the actual negatives that were incorrectly identified by the model. These metrics rely on the following classification outcomes: True Positives (TP), which represent correctly identified abnormal behaviors; False Positives (FP), which correspond to normal behaviors incorrectly classified as abnormal; True Negatives (TN), which are correctly classified normal behaviors; and False Negatives (FN), which refer to abnormal behaviors that the model failed to detect.

On the other hand, PR AUC focuses on the model's ability to correctly predict positive cases at various levels of recall, particularly when the positive class is rare. This makes it a more suitable and reliable evaluation metric for imbalanced datasets, where the positive class (e.g., abnormal behaviors) is rare. As shown in Eq. (8), PR AUC is computed using precision (Eq. (4)), which measures the proportion of predicted positives that were actually positive, and recall (Eq. (5)), which measures the proportion of actual positives that were successfully identified by the model.

The TensorFlow¹³ library is employed in this work to utilize multiple thresholds with a number that defaults to 200 for computing the pairs of recall and precision values. Additionally, a score of 50% is considered the floor (random classifier) for ROC AUC, while for PR AUC, this is determined as the positive rate of the data.

Since both metrics are designed for binary classification, a One-vs-All (OvA) or a One-vs-Rest (OvR) approach is applied for multiclass classification problems.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{TPR} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{FPR} = \frac{FP}{FP + TN} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{PR AUC} = \int_0^1 \text{Precision}(\text{Recall}) d(\text{Recall}) \quad (8)$$

$$\text{ROC AUC} = \int_0^1 \text{TPR}(\text{FPR}) d(\text{FPR}) \quad (9)$$

V. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

This section presents the experimental evaluation of the PSCS-I dataset and its variations compared to baseline datasets. First, the binary classification results are reported and discussed, including both within-dataset and cross-dataset evaluation setups. Next, the results of the multiclass classification experiments are provided, based on evaluations conducted on the respective test sets of each benchmark dataset, including PSCS-I.

A. BINARY CLASSIFICATION EXPERIMENTS

For the binary classification experiments, Table 3 presents the performance on the corresponding test sets of UMN, MED, Movies Fights, UBI Fights, SCVD, WVD, PSCS-I Synthetic, PSCS-I Enhanced, and PSCS-I Union datasets of the CrimeNet architecture trained on the training set of the respective datasets. The reported performance for all of the imbalanced datasets (PR AUC) surpasses 93% while exceeding 99% on the MED, UBI Fights, and SCVD. The latter observation is also applicable to the balanced dataset, Movies Fights, where ROC AUC is employed as the primary metric. Indeed, the model trained using the Movies Fights dataset achieved a perfect ROC AUC of 100%.

The performance on the PSCS-I surpasses 90%, slightly lower compared to the rest of the datasets; however, this can be considered promising as it might be a result of the fact that the PSCS-I encompasses more challenging behaviors assigned to normal (e.g., social considered as normal) and

TABLE 3. Binary classification performance of the CrimeNet architecture trained on PSCS-I variations and different abnormal and violent crowd behavior datasets, evaluated on each dataset’s respective test set. The "*" denotes the ROC AUC score, used as the primary metric for balanced datasets.

Trained Model	(PRIROC*) AUC
UMN [19]	96.19%
MED [17]	100.00%
Movies Fights [20]	100.00%*
UBI Fights [35]	99.97%
SCVD [21]	100.00%
WVD [38]	96.06%
PSCS-I Synthetic	94.74%
PSCS-I Enhanced	94.13%
PSCS-I Union	93.10%
PSCS-I Synthetic Static	92.75%

abnormal (e.g., mixed-running considered as abnormal) for the binary classification. On the other hand, the benchmark datasets are either binary annotated, or their normal and abnormal behaviors are highly separable (e.g., panic vs. normal for the UMN dataset).

For the PSCS-I Enhanced, a slightly lower PR AUC (94.13%) is observed compared to PSCS-I Synthetic (94.74%), which can be attributed to the incorporation of two video types that target the characteristics of two different real-world datasets that increase the complexity during training. This reduction is also observed between the PSCS-I Union and PSCS-I Enhanced variations, where the PR AUC is decreased by 1.03% for the PSCS-I Union. This is expected considering that the PSCS-I Union includes additional videos from the PSCS-I Synthetic variation compared to PSCS-I Enhanced, and thus, the training complexity is further increased. However, for both models trained on the PSCS-I Enhanced and PSCS-I Union variations, the performance is still close to the one obtained using PSCS-I Synthetic, indicating that the enhanced data does not provide a significant contribution in a within-dataset evaluation setup. This observation also aligns with the findings reported for enhanced data generated from the CARLA simulator in a semantic segmentation task [27]. Regarding the PSCS-I Synthetic Static variation, the within-dataset performance remains close to the one achieved with the entire dataset (PSCS-I Synthetic), and thus, it is concluded that these properties do not add an increased complexity in binary classification settings. This can be attributed to the fact that in binary classification, the model can more easily distinguish if a frame is considered abnormal based on the camera movements introduced by the BWC perspective and the earthquake events during abnormal events, since it is limited to normal and abnormal classes.

B. CROSS-DATASET EXPERIMENTS

In this subsection, we present the results on cross-dataset binary classification to illustrate the generalization capabilities of the models trained on the proposed PSCS-I dataset and its variations compared to the existing crowd behavior analysis datasets. To validate the effectiveness of the photorealism

¹³https://www.tensorflow.org/api_docs/python/tf/keras/metrics/AUC

TABLE 4. Similarity evaluation of the PSCS-I dataset, its photorealism enhanced variations, WVD, and CrowdFlow, compared to the initial datasets employed to train the photorealism enhancement method (EPE) and the crowd behavior analysis related datasets. The CMMD metric is utilized to evaluate similarity. Lower values indicate higher similarity between the datasets. Bold indicates the most similar and underlined the second most similar synthetic dataset for each real-world dataset.

Synthetic Datasets	EPE Real-World Datasets		Crowd Behavior Real-World Datasets				
	Cityscapes	KITTI	UMN	MED	Movies Fights	UBI Fights	SCVD
CrowdFlow [37]	7.182	6.985	7.443	8.255	7.447	6.728	7.329
WVD [38]	7.291	6.987	7.313	7.181	5.276	4.978	4.755
PSCS-I Synthetic	6.105	6.053	6.046	6.457	5.081	4.632	5.154
PSCS-I Enhanced-Cityscapes	<u>5.773</u>	<u>5.752</u>	5.956	6.392	<u>4.644</u>	<u>4.556</u>	5.160
PSCS-I Enhanced-KITTI	5.135	5.028	5.415	5.984	4.221	4.135	<u>4.896</u>

TABLE 5. Cross-dataset binary classification evaluation of trained models on the imbalanced datasets UMN, MED, UBI Fights, SCVD, and PSCS-I variations, and the balanced dataset, Movies Fights, using PR AUC and PR ROC as the primary metric, respectively. Bold values indicate the best performance across training datasets for each evaluation dataset. The "*" denotes the ROC AUC score, used as the primary metric for the balanced dataset.

Training Dataset	Evaluation Dataset				
	UMN	MED	Movies Fights	UBI Fights	SCVD
UMN [19]	-	60.93%	44.05%*	95.84%	48.38%
MED [17]	32.86%	-	44.05%*	48.35%	49.56%
Movies Fights [20]	42.43%	41.51%	-	30.95%	61.94%
UBI Fights [35]	77.39%	52.29%	52.84%*	-	52.29%
SCVD [21]	43.34%	43.33%	47.49%*	30.90%	-
WVD [38]	38.23%	40.46%	40.12%*	42.60%	67.60%
PSCS-I Synthetic	74.02%	62.81%	60.44%*	95.39%	41.24%
PSCS-I Enhanced	76.87%	64.44%	50.73%*	96.06%	38.00%
PSCS-I Union	78.04%	64.89%	62.62%*	95.46%	43.11%
PSCS-I Synthetic Static	79.82%	62.74%	42.84%*	93.41%	37.96%

enhancement, we first evaluate the PSCS-I and its variations along with two synthetic datasets, namely synthetic WVD and CrowdFlow, in terms of similarity with real-world datasets. Then we present and discuss the binary cross-domain evaluation results on the task at hand (crowd behavior classification).

1) Similarity Evaluation

The similarity in terms of photorealism of the PSCS-I Synthetic, PSCS-I Enhanced-Cityscapes, PSCS-I Enhanced-KITTI, synthetic WVD, and CrowdFlow datasets compared to the initial datasets employed to train EPE, namely Cityscapes and KITTI, and the crowd behavior analysis datasets UMN, MED, Movies Fights, UBI Fights, and SCVD are provided in Table 4. As illustrated, both PSCS-I Enhanced-Cityscapes and PSCS-I Enhanced-KITTI have higher similarity than the one observed with the PSCS-I Synthetic dataset when comparing them with the respective datasets that were used for training EPE (Cityscapes and KITTI). This indicates that while the pretrained EPE models were trained on the CARLA simulator, which is an outdoor simulator for autonomous driving, the translation results remain effective. This is attributed to the fact that EPE learns to enhance the photorealism of objects (or groups of objects) individually based on the semantic segmentation while also relying on the properties of the objects, such as their geometry and materials, rather than the entire virtual scene. Moreover, the tendency of higher similarity of the enhanced variations

continues with most of the real-world datasets (UMN, MED, Movies Fights, and UBI Fights) related to crowd behavior analysis with PSCS-I Enhanced-KITTI, providing the highest degree of photorealism, which also aligns with our observation when qualitatively comparing the results. It is notable that while the PSCS-I Synthetic variation is less similar to the real-world datasets due to the sim2real appearance gap, it still manages substantial improvement compared to the existing synthetic WVD and CrowdFlow. Indeed, this is reflected by the lower CMMD metric with UMN, MED, Movies Fights, and UBI Fight compared to the CMMD observed for synthetic WVD and CrowdFlow. This highlights the increased degree of photorealism of the PSCS-I dataset that stems from the employment of UE5, accompanied by all the latest technologies and the high-quality assets that were used to generate the proposed dataset. The only exception that is not aligned with the aforementioned observations is for the real-world SCVD dataset, which illustrates the highest similarity with the synthetic WVD and a comparable one with the PSCS-I Enhanced-KITTI. This may be attributed to more distortion, artifacts, or blurriness produced by the cameras or the video quality of the SCVD dataset.

2) Binary Classification Cross-Evaluation

Focusing on the generalization capabilities of the CrimeNet architecture when employing the PSCS-I dataset and thus the evaluation of the sim2real appearance gap between the PSCS-I variations and the real-world data on the task at hand (be-

FIGURE 7. Confusion matrices for the top three best-performing models, cross-evaluated on the Movies Fights dataset for abnormal behavior detection (binary classification).

havior classification), the cross-dataset evaluation results on the imbalanced datasets—UMN, MED, and UBI Fights—and the balanced dataset, Movies Fights, are shown in Table 5. Across most imbalanced datasets (UMN, MED, UBI Fights, and SCVD), the trained models using the PSCS-I variations achieve the best performance in PR AUC, which indicates higher generalization capabilities. In detail, the model trained on the PSCS-I Union dataset achieves a PR AUC score of 78.04% on the UMN dataset, surpassing the performance of the model trained on the larger-scale UBI Fights dataset. Furthermore, when evaluated on the MED dataset, the PSCS-I Union-trained model reports a score of 64.89%, outperforming the model trained on the abnormal-related UMN dataset. The same observation applies for the UBI Fights evaluation, where a PR AUC of 96.06% is observed for the PSCS-I Enhanced trained model. The latter high PR AUC for UBI Fights also aligns with the high similarity that is observed between this dataset and the PSCS-I Synthetic and its enhanced variations.

On the other hand, the CrimeNet architecture trained on the synthetic WVD dataset demonstrated moderate performance across most datasets with the exception of SCVD, where a PR AUC of 67.60% is achieved. This might be a result of the fact that the synthetic WVD is a dataset that shares the exact same classes with SCVD, in addition to the lower CMMD (highest similarity) between these datasets (WVD and SCVD) compared to the ones observed for the PSCS-I and its enhanced variations, including a weaponized class. Regarding the balanced dataset, Movies Fights, the models trained on the UMN, UBI Fights, WVD, SCVD, and MED datasets struggle to generalize, with an ROC AUC (primary metric for balanced datasets) score close to or below random guessing. However, the PSCS-I Synthetic and Union-trained models, despite being trained on an imbalanced dataset, were the only ones to achieve a performance above random

guessing. Specifically, the PSCS-I Union variation achieved the highest ROC AUC of 62.62%, outperforming by 9.78% the second-best result that was reached when training the CrimeNet architecture with the UBI Fights dataset.

The PSCS-I Synthetic static subset proved to maintain comparable performance (MED, UBI Fights, and SCVD) or even 5.8% higher PR AUC for UMN compared to the PSCS-I Synthetic variation, which aligns with the fact that utilizing dynamic cameras (e.g., phone cameras and BWC) for crowd behavior analysis through static CCTV cameras (UMN, MED, and SCVD) doesn't significantly contribute to generalization or can even alter the distribution of the CCTV-based behavior detection and thus lead to worse results [21]. The only significant increase that favors the PSCS-I Synthetic variation compared to the static subset is for the Movies Fights cross-evaluation, where PSCS-I Synthetic demonstrates an increase of 17.6% for the ROC AUC metric. Particularly, this increase is attributed to the fact that Movies Fights is a dataset that comprises footage captured from action movies and thus contains frequent and intense camera movements. An ideal setup to evaluate the generalization capabilities of the PSCS-I dataset would be to utilize a real-world dataset captured through a BWC. However, such a real-world dataset currently does not exist.

Concerning the models trained on the PSCS-I variations, those that utilized the photorealism-enhanced videos during the learning process, and specifically the PSCS-I Union variation, consistently outperform the respective model trained on the PSCS-I Synthetic variation. This finding indicates that the enhanced data can indeed improve the abnormal detection performance of the models that are to be applied to real-world data. However, the difference is significantly more limited compared to other computer vision tasks, such as semantic segmentation [27], that operate at the pixel level of the RGB images instead of relying on the motion extracted through

traditional optical flow algorithms (i.e., Gunnar-Farneback), which are primarily based on mathematical assumptions (e.g., brightness constancy, spatial smoothness) rather than learned features sensitive to domain-specific appearance. In detail, CrimeNet is an architecture that heavily relies on the predicted motion instead of the RGB images. Moreover, in the PSCS-I Union, the reported performance increases PR AUC for UMN, MED, Movies Fights, and SCVD compared to employing only the enhanced data (PSCS-I Enhanced), which, in the case of Movies Fights and SCVD, leads to a decreased accuracy. This is an expected finding considering that the PSCS-I-Enhanced variation contains fewer unique training videos (see Section III-B4), which highlights that the diversity related to the crowd behaviors and the environments is also important for performing in cross-domain real-world datasets.

In particular, when evaluating on Movies Fights, the model trained on the PSCS-I Enhanced achieved a PR AUC of 50.73%, which is significantly worse than the PR AUC of 60.44% reached by the model trained on the PSCS-I Synthetic. This suggests that the performance was largely driven by the unique videos that are not included in the enhanced variation of the PSCS-I dataset. Indeed, when these additional synthetic videos, excluded from the enhanced set due to generative AI restrictions, were included, the model trained using PSCS-I Union outperformed the one trained using the PSCS-I Synthetic by 2.18%. This improvement highlights the combined benefits of reducing the sim2real appearance gap with the photorealism enhancement method while additionally leveraging the remaining unique synthetic videos as training data in order to improve the diversity.

The aforementioned observations are further illustrated in Fig. 7, where the confusion matrices of the three best-performing models (PSCS-I Synthetic, PSCS-I Union, UBI Fights), PSCS-I cross-evaluated on the Movies Fights dataset after calculating the optimal threshold, are presented. In detail, 0.0251 was selected as the optimal minimum threshold to consider a prediction abnormal for the PSCS-I Synthetic-trained model, 0.0352 for the PSCS-I Union-trained model, and 0.3467 for the UBI Fights-trained model. As depicted, the model trained on the PSCS-I synthetic variation achieves 70% in detecting normal behaviors, while this accuracy is decreased to 62% for the abnormal ones. On the other hand, the model trained on PSCS-I Union increases the normal detection accuracy by 2% and the abnormal by 9%. The model trained using UBI Fights achieved the third-best performance, being the largest dataset in terms of frames, but it struggles to predict the abnormal class (34% accuracy) effectively. This indicates that while the UBI Fights dataset includes a larger volume of frames, its diversity in terms of behaviors and environments is rather limited.

Furthermore, by comparing the results observed during the within-dataset evaluation presented in Table 3 with the cross-dataset evaluation in Table 5, it becomes evident that the models that achieved a perfect accuracy of 100% during the within-dataset evaluation are prone to overfitting. Indeed, the

models trained on MED, Movie Fights, and SCVD illustrate substandard generalization capabilities. On the other hand, the model trained on the proposed PSCS-I dataset, despite achieving a lower PR AUC on its respective test set, has significantly higher performance on most of the cross-datasets (UMN, MED, Movie Fights, and UBI Fights). This suggests that the proposed dataset better captures the complexities of the real-world crowd behaviors, and thus the model is less prone to overfitting. Furthermore, by employing the enhanced data as training data, the within-dataset PR AUC further decreases while the generalization capacity of the model is increased. This is attributed to the sim2real appearance gap that exists in synthetic data, which still fails to capture the visual complexities of the real world.

Finally, Table 6 presents the cross-evaluation of PSCS-I Synthetic, PSCS-I Enhanced, and PSCS-I Union on the indoor-only (UBI Fights-Indoor) and outdoor-only (UBI Fights-Outdoor) subsets of UBI Fights. As expected, considering the focus of the dataset in indoor environments, there is an impact on performance when cross-evaluating in outdoor scenes compared to the indoor ones of roughly 11% for the PSCS-I Synthetic trained model, 13% for PSCS-I Enhanced, and 15% for PSCS-I Union. However, the highest AUC PR that was achieved using the model trained on the PSCS-I Synthetic subset (88.57%) is still considered a relatively high accuracy for a model that was trained solely on indoor-only scenes. This highlights the potential extensibility of the PSCS-I to also outdoor-only settings despite its current focus on indoor environments. Although PSCS-I Synthetic achieves the highest PR AUC in outdoors environments (compared to the other PSCS-I variations), its predictions are less consistent when considering both indoor and outdoor scenes together (lower PR AUC in Table 5 compared to PSCS-I Enhanced and PSCS-I Union). In contrast, PSCS-I Enhanced and PSCS-I Union provide more balanced and stable predictions across both domains (on the entire UBI Fights dataset), which makes them more robust in combined evaluations. This again indicates that photorealistic enhancement (PSCS-I Enhanced) and its combination (PSCS-I Union) improve generalization.

TABLE 6. Cross-evaluation of the PSCS-I-trained models on the indoor- and outdoor-only subsets of UBI Fights. AUC PR is employed as the evaluation metric.

Method	UBI Fights-Indoor	UBI Fights-Outdoor
PSCS-I Synthetic	97.29%	88.57%
PSCS-I Enhanced	97.67%	86.57%
PSCS-I Union	97.32%	84.86%

C. MULTICLASS CLASSIFICATION EXPERIMENTS

In this section, we present and discuss the experimental results using the proposed PSCS-I dataset in a multiclass manner. To provide a comprehensive evaluation and highlight the contribution of both the BWC perspective and the trigger events included in the PSCS-I dataset, we additionally employ a specific subset of the dataset, referred to as PSCS-I Synthetic Static. As there are currently no publicly available

TABLE 7. Evaluation of models trained for the multiclass evaluation using the PSCS-I Synthetic variation. Results are shown for the full PSCS-I Synthetic variation and the filtered PSCS-I Synthetic Static subset, which excludes the BWC perspective and earthquake-trigger events. Performance is reported using PR AUC scores based on an OvR strategy. For the baseline datasets, MED, SCVD, and WVD, only the average PR AUC is reported. Bold values indicate the best performance, and values in parentheses denote the positive ratio for each class.

Training Dataset	Behavior Classes					Average
	Walking	Social	Evacuation	Mixed Running	Aggressive/Fighting	
MED [17]			–			99.93%
SCVD [21]			–			100.00%
WVD [38]			–			81.89%
PSCS-I Synthetic	91.41% (66.48%)	79.78% (27.58%)	31.64% (1.41%)	13.92% (2.25%)	50.78% (2.25%)	53.50%
PSCS-I Synthetic Static	96.86% (69.58%)	93.16% (24.25%)	49.93% (1.06%)	25.76% (1.06%)	64.78% (3.39%)	66.09%

(a) Earthquake (b) BWC (c) BWC (d) Static

FIGURE 8. Optical flow calculated with the Gunnar-Farneback algorithm between two consecutive frames for earthquake, BWC, and trigger events, along with an indicative sample from the PSCS-I Synthetic Static subset.

multiclass behavior analysis datasets that share the same classes included in PSCS-I, only the average performance is reported for the multi-class baseline datasets (MED, SCVD, and synthetic WVD). Moreover, as a result, no cross-domain experiments are conducted, and thus, the additional PSCS-I variations (PSCS-I Union and PSCS-I Enhanced) are not utilized.

Along those lines, Table 7 illustrates the performance of the CrimeNet architecture trained for multiclass behavior classification using the PSCS-I Synthetic and PSCS-Synthetic Static subset. Specifically, both the per-class following the OvR strategy and the average PR AUC are reported. In detail, as observed in the table, the PR AUC score surpasses 99% for the MED, reaches a perfect accuracy of 100% for SCVD, and achieves a more moderate 80% for the synthetic WVD. However, when utilizing the PSCS-I Synthetic as the benchmark dataset, the PR AUC is significantly lower compared to the aforementioned datasets, with an average PR AUC of 53.50%. This lower performance on the PSCS-I Synthetic compared to the baseline datasets is a noteworthy outcome since it indicates that the dataset poses a more challenging and realistic classification task without overfitting.

After removing the BWC perspective and the earthquake trigger events using the PSCS-I Synthetic Static, an increase to a PR AUC of 66.09% is observed compared to utilizing the PSCS-I Synthetic. This indicates that the motion introduced by the earthquake and BWC makes the classification of the behaviors more difficult since it introduces further com-

plexity, making it more challenging to distinguish between abnormal-related classes in the optical flow. Indeed, as depicted in Fig. 8-a, 8-b, and 8-c, when the camera moves due to an earthquake event or the motion of a person equipped with a BWC, the entire scene exhibits motion, creating a global optical flow that overlays the actual movement of characters in the crowd. On the other hand, when the camera remains static as illustrated in Figure 8-d, the motion is restricted to the movement of the depicted characters.

Finally, Fig. 9 illustrates the confusion matrices for the PSCS-I Synthetic variation and the PSCS-I Synthetic Static subset. It is observed that the most challenging classes in the PSCS-I Synthetic are the evacuation and mixed running classes, with an accuracy lower than 10%. In detail, the model achieves the strongest performance on the normal-related classes, walking and social, with an accuracy of 98% and 47%, respectively. On the other hand, when employing the PSCS-I Synthetic static subset, the accuracy of all the classes is substantially increased, with the highest accuracy reached again from the normal classes of walking (97%) and social (75%). Additionally, the accuracy of the aggressive/fighting class received a superior relevant improvement of 178% in PSCS-I Synthetic Static compared to the PSCS-I Synthetic subset. This highlights that the inclusion of the BWC and earthquake trigger events introduces additional complexity to the dataset, demonstrating that even the SoTA CrimeNet architecture is challenged. Consequently, the goal of introducing a dataset that can serve as a benchmark for future methods,

FIGURE 9. Confusion matrices of the multiclass PSCS-I Synthetic models: (a) trained on the filtered dataset excluding the earthquake trigger events and the BWC perspective, and (b) trained on the complete PSCS-I Synthetic dataset.

enabling the observation of meaningful performance differences compared to the baselines, is achieved.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a novel indoor crowd analysis synthetic dataset for Photorealistic Synthetic Crowds Simulation in Indoor environments (PSCS-I) is proposed. We developed a realistic crowd simulation environment and a comprehensive data generation pipeline that can automatically produce highly accurate crowd behavior annotations. Considering that synthetic data is fed to models that are to be deployed in the real world, we also applied a photorealism enhancement method that was evaluated in terms of similarity with real-world datasets and proved to further improve the photorealism of the rendered frames.

To evaluate the contribution of the proposed dataset, extensive experiments using the SotA crowd behavior analysis approach, CrimeNet, were performed. The experiments illustrated that the proposed dataset introduces a significant challenge to the CrimeNet architecture for multiclass crowd behavior classification. The photorealism enhancement method was also proven to further improve the generalization capacity of the model when applied to real-world datasets. Models trained with the PSCS-I variations that included the photorealism-enhanced data outperformed those that utilized the existing datasets in cross-dataset evaluation for abnormal crowd behavior detection. Additionally, while PSCS-I is an indoor-focused dataset, it demonstrated potential extensibility to outdoor environments with a small impact on accuracy. Building on this study's focus on indoor environments, we plan to extend our work to outdoor environments as a next step, including a dynamic drone camera, varying times and weather conditions, and a larger number of characters.

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APPENDIX A PHOTOREALISM ENHANCEMENT QUALITATIVE RESULTS

Figure 10 presents qualitative results of sample rendered frames of the PSCS-I dataset (PSCS-I Synthetic), including their translation towards the characteristics of the real-world datasets KITTI (PSCS-I Enhanced-KITTI) and Cityscapes (PSCS-I Enhanced-Cityscapes) by employing EPE. Additionally, sample frames are illustrated from the synthetic WVD and the real-world UBI Fights datasets. It is evident that despite using the latest version of the engine, namely UE5, and new technologies that improve the lighting of the scene, such as ray-tracing and lumen, the rendered images appear with neutral and faded colors with less hard shadows. Moreover, there are issues with pixelation or artifacts that can be triggered by the processes used by the graphics pipeline, such as anti-aliasing. The photorealism-enhanced frames generated by EPE reduce these issues by increasing the intensity of the light and the shadows and changing the scene at the material level based on the target real-world dataset. In detail, EPE considers the real-world dataset that was utilized dur-

FIGURE 10. Qualitative comparison of sample frames from the PSCS-I dataset, including the original rendered videos (PSCS-I Synthetic), their translations toward the characteristics of KITTI (PSCS-I Enhanced-KITTI) and Cityscapes (PSCS-I Enhanced-Cityscapes), alongside sample frames from the synthetic WVD dataset and real-world UBI Fights videos.

ing training as reality. Thus, for KITTI (PSCS-I Enhanced-KITTI), the results are significantly brighter and more colorful, while for Cityscapes (PSCS-I Enhanced-Cityscapes), they are darker and grayer.

Synthetic WVD is also a synthetic dataset that was extracted through the game, GTA-V. The sample frames of the dataset are more colorful and vivid compared to PSCS-I Synthetic; however, the colors remain faded and non-realistic with less hard shadows. In addition, the dataset has significant pixelation due to anti-aliasing, particularly around the characters, which are the object of interest in crowd analysis. Finally, concerning the real-world UBI Fights frames, it is apparent that the color distribution doesn't always align with the one produced by the rendered image of the PSCS-I, the enhanced variations, or the synthetic WVD. The color distribution alone is not a sufficient criterion for determining the photorealism of a synthetic dataset. In fact, even in the case where identical real-world scenes in terms of content and colors were reconstructed through a game engine, the synthetic datasets would still suffer from the sim2real appearance gap due to the reduced complexity compared to the real-world with regard to the lighting, the shadows, and the materials and surface properties (e.g., glossiness). For instance, Virtual KITTI [72] is a dataset that reconstructed the real-world KITTI dataset

through the Unity engine¹⁴. The dataset was later updated in a second version, Virtual KITTI 2 [73], with higher quality materials and newer improvements in lighting and post-processing to reduce the sim2real appearance gap that existed in the first version, despite the identical content and colors.

APPENDIX B BINARY CLASSIFICATION CROSS-EVALUATION ADDITIONAL EXPERIMENTS

In this appendix section, we present additional cross-evaluation experiments by employing the 3D-ResNet [59] architecture. In detail, 3D ResNet is an extension of the ResNet [74] architecture that takes as input a sequence of frames to perform binary or multiclass classification. The architecture has been widely employed for video classification, including crowd violence detection [2], [4], [75]. Particularly, we employed the PSCS-I synthetic variation for an application that aimed to detect violent incidents through static CCTV cameras. Thus, for this case, the dataset was filtered to exclude the panic-related classes, namely, evacuation and mixed running, and the BWC perspective. Considering that 3D ResNet performs video classification, the PSCS-I dataset was split into videos that correspond to the normal (walking or social) and violence (aggressive/fighting) classes. Since each

¹⁴<https://unity.com/>

PSCS-I full-length video contains a single aggressive/fighting event that is triggered at a random timestamp of the video with a duration of roughly 30 seconds, this resulted in two normal and one violent footage per full-length video.

For training, the entire dataset was employed, and 20% was randomly split and utilized as a validation set. In detail, the 3D ResNet-50 architecture pretrained on the Kinetics [76] dataset was used to finetune on the training samples for five epochs in total. The best-performing model based on the validation loss was preserved for testing. The same setup was followed with the Movies Fights, SCVD, and synthetic WVD datasets, which are the only datasets that were employed in the CrimeNet experiments that are provided for video classification (each video belongs to a single class). To evaluate the performance in terms of accuracy, a cross-evaluation strategy similar to CrimeNet was performed using the ROC AUC for the balanced Movies Fights and PR AUC for the imbalanced SCVD dataset. Specifically, Table 8 presents the cross-evaluation results of the 3D ResNet-50 models finetuned on Movies Fights, SCVD, synthetic WVD, and PSCS-I, cross-evaluated on the real-world datasets Movies Fights and SCVD. It is evident that the model trained on the PSCS-I Synthetic dataset manages to achieve the highest level of generalization across both the Movies Fights and the SCVD datasets. Additionally, the synthetic WVD leads to the lowest metrics for both Movies Fights and SCVD datasets. Considering that 3D ResNet utilizes only the RGB images instead of additional information, such as optical flow extracted from traditional algorithms (e.g., Gunnar-Farneback [62]) that are less affected by the sim2real appearance gap, the low ROC AUC and PR AUC scores of the WVD-trained model are an expected observation.

TABLE 8. Cross-dataset binary classification evaluation of finetuned 3D ResNet-50 models on the imbalanced SCVD dataset and the balanced Movies Fights dataset, using PR AUC and PR ROC as the primary metric, respectively. Bold values indicate the best performance across training datasets for each evaluation dataset. The "*" denotes the ROC AUC score, used as the primary metric for the balanced dataset.

Training Dataset	Evaluation Dataset	
	Movies	SCVD
Movies [20]	-	85.02%
SCVD [21]	80.52%*	-
WVD [38]	42.81%*	50.80%
PSCS-I Synthetic	93.63%*	93.06%

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